

MoveD – ORD Guidelines for Swiss Movement Laboratories

Section 6: Data Sharing

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Before a licence can be issued or data shared, the copyright must be owned by the person granting the licence/sharing the data. Clarify with your supervisor or the data security officer what is applicable in your institution.

1. Licences

1.1 Context

- Licences are crucial in terms of regulating the sharing of data and source code/software. They offer both data/source code creators and users a framework for rights, responsibilities, permissions, and forms of redistribution. For data creators, licences ensure proper attribution, the protection of their property rights, and control over derivatives. For users, on the other hand, licences ensure legal compliance.
- The listed licences (CC, Copyleft, permissive licences) are commonly used for publication of data and source code/software, but note that this list is not exhaustive, and many other licences (including custom licences) can be used. Ensure that any chosen licence conforms to your institutional requirements and rules.

1.2 Remark regarding CC licences:

- Licences and CC0 cannot be revoked
- A CC licence cannot be granted for software and hardware.
- It is necessary to clearly state which part of the work is being licensed
- Additional requirements for the further use of the data may also be attached to the licence

The following questions have to be answered at the beginning of the project:

1. How is the data to be used? For example, if it is to appear in a Wikipedia article, it needs at least BY-SA.
2. Are there licence requirements from the funding institution?
3. Is the data to be transmitted with compulsory attribution?
4. Should the data be allowed to be used commercially?
5. May the data be edited and modified?
6. Should changes be allowed to be published by others under any conditions?

Table 1: Available licences that can be granted.

Licence name	Description	Keywords
CC BY – attribution (see also “permissive licences”)	“...enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, even commercially, as long as attribution is given to the creator.”	Sharing and editing possible when giving attribution to the creator
CC BY-SA – attribution & sharing under the same terms (see also “Copyleft”)	“...enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format even for commercial use, as long as attribution is given to the creator. Adaptations must be shared under the same terms.”	Distribution under the same conditions, sharing and editing possible with attribution

CC BY-ND – attribution & no derivatives or adaptations	“...enables reusers to copy and distribute the material in any medium or format in unadapted form only, also for commercial use, and only as long as attribution is given to the creator.”	Sharing when giving attribution, but no passing on of edits
CC BY-NC – attribution & non-commercial use	“...enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format for non-commercial purposes only, and only as long as attribution is given to the creator.”	Sharing and editing possible with attribution and non-commercial use
CC BY-NC-SA – attribution, non-commercial & sharing under the same terms	“...enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format for non-commercial purposes only, as long as attribution is given to the creator. Adaptations must be shared under the same terms.”	Sharing and editing possible with attribution and for non-commercial use, but redistribution only under the same conditions
CC BY-NC-ND – attribution, non-commercial, no derivatives or adaptations	“...enables reusers to copy and distribute the material in any medium or format in unadapted form only, for non-commercial purposes only, and only as long as attribution is given to the creator.”	Sharing possible with attribution, non-commercial, but no sharing of derivatives
CC-0	The creator gives up the copyright and puts the work into the worldwide public domain.	No copyright
Copyleft (GPL, LGPL, MPL, CC BY-SA ...)	Copyleft licences allow for modification (reuse, remixing, adaptation) of the original work, on condition that the derived work is published under the same or a similar licence.	Distribution under the same conditions, sharing and editing possible with attribution
Permissive licences (BSD, MIT, Apache, CC BY) (Fossa Editorial Team, 2021)	Permissive licences allow the modification (reuse, remixing, adaptation) of the original work, without any restrictions and/or obligations.	Sharing and editing possible when giving attribution to the creator

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2. Informed consent

To openly share data, a corresponding section (see 4.3 informed consent form) must be included in the informed consent form. A statement that the necessary informed consent has been collected from the participants must be included in the metadata when sharing data in a repository.

3. Choosing a repository to publish data

The following criteria should be taken into consideration when choosing a repository to publish the data. The criteria are discussed with commonly used general data repositories in mind, but similar limitations and criteria are likely to apply to other general or field-specific data repositories. Basically, the FAIR principles should be applied. Please check with your institution or funding agency if specific repositories are recommended.

In SNF and EU projects, data should be published in repositories that fulfil the FAIR principles. In EU projects the policy is “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. In EU projects, metadata must be published under CC0 or a similar license. For SNF projects the FAIR principles apply to data and metadata.

Table 2: Considerations when choosing a repository (Stall et al., 2023).

Criterion	Considerations	Comment
File size limitations	Individual file size limitations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some data repositories limit the size of individual files, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Limit of 2-5 GB: Harvard data repository; OSF. ○ Limit of 5TB: Figshare. ○ No file limit specified (see total limit below): Dryad, Mendeley Data, Vivli, Zenodo. Total dataset limitation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most data repositories also include a limitation for the total dataset: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Up to 10 GB: OSF (not public data). ○ Up to 100 GB: Figshare (free), OSF (public data), Zenodo. ○ Up to 1 TB: Dryad, Zenodo (total limit per researcher). ○ Up to 10 GB: Figshare (non-free). 	
Licence conditions	In some repositories, data can only be published using specific licence conditions. Note that most repositories require metadata to be published with a CC0 licence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dryad only allows CC0 for data. • Vivli uses a custom licence. • Other repositories offer a choice (typically including CC; GPL; MIT; Apache). 	Institutional limitations/rules may need to be considered on this point. See 1. Licences
Supported export formats (Accessibility/ Interoperability)	To facilitate the export and reusability of data, consider which data formats or export methods have direct export built into the repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JSON and XML: supported in all major repositories listed in this guideline • API-Export: Dryad, Figshare • All formats: Vivli 	

Patient data security/ identifiable patient data	<p>There may be some cases where identifiable data should be accessible by select people (e.g. directly involved researchers or medical staff on the project). This may affect the choice of repository, depending on repository rules and support for identifiable data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No support for identifiable data (i.e. identifiable data not allowed): Harvard Dataverse Repository, Figshare, Mendeley, OSF. • Limited support for anonymised personal data: Dryad, Zenodo. • Support for limited access to personal data: Vivli. 	
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4. Metadata

The following information should be collected before data is published.

Table 3: Metadata used for data publication.

Title	Content/Format	Comment
General information		
Date of data publication	[YYYY-MM-DD]	According to International Organization for Standardization 8601
Used data format(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .CSV • .RData • .txt • ... 	Data in structured and open-source format. Open Formats are described in the document "Section 3: Process": examples are json, xml, rdf, csv, txt, odf, ooxml, tiff, jpeg
Licence type for data reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CC-level (0, BY, BY-SA, BY-ND, BY-NC, BY-NC-SA, BY-NC-ND) • Custom licence, depending on institutional rules 	Details can be found in 1. Licences
Stage of data processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data • Processed data (cut/normalized and after quality check) • Summarized statistics (means, sd, interquartile ranges, ...) 	
Storage location/ name of file for nomenclature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • File or storage location where the description of the used nomenclature (see marker model) is saved 	

Information on encoding/anonymization		
Encoding/ anonymization of personal data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anonymization method Responsible person including contact information (email, phone) 	The responsible person is usually the Principal Investigator. Please discuss it within your project team
Anonymization of quantitative movement data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify the method that was applied to anonymize quantitative data (for example the use of summarized instead of raw data; using simulated data based on the original data; introduction of statistical error to raw data) 	
Information on the data content (description of single files)		
Information on data collection	Include information on the different tests/measurements that have been carried out, and in which files the results of each test/measurement have been saved	Refer to content of the document "Section 2: Collect"
Information on participants/their characteristics	See 4.1 Collect metadata	
Information on movement data	See 4.1 Collect metadata	
Information on data analysis		
Repository/ location where the data has been stored	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimal requirement: URL or repository and dataset name Best practices: provide a repository name and link (e.g. GitHub-Release) and a URI, so the exact version of data can be tracked (e.g. use a repository DOI; GitHub + Zenodo to generate a DOI for the GitHub release) 	
Funding information and acknowledgement		
Information on funding	Include information on the funding agency and grant number (if applicable). Please also describe if the funding was from within the university	
Acknowledgement	People or institutions that assisted in the research project	

If statistical analysis was performed with R, Python, Julia or Observable JS, code of the statistical analysis can be published with Quarto. More information is available on their website quarto.org.

5. Data

The following information should be collected during the data publication process. It is possible to store the information either in two separate files (e.g. one with movement data and one with the personal data of participants) or in one file containing all the information. In all cases, the metadata should be uploaded separately and NOT to the same file as the data. Please consider the download time when deciding if the data needs to be split between several files e.g. one file for each condition or one file for each data type (e.g. EMG, kinematics, or kinetics).

Table 4: Information in data to be published in a repository.

Title	Content/Format	Comment
General information		
Stage of data processing (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data • Processed data cut/normalized without quality check • Processed data cut/normalized and after quality check • Summarized statistics 	More than one option possible
Kinematic, kinetic, spatiotemporal, or EMG data		
Stage of data processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data • Angle data (cut/normalized and after quality check) • Moments (cut/normalized and after quality check) • Forces (cut/normalized and after quality check) • Spatiotemporal parameters (cut/normalized and after quality check) • Normalized data (after quality check) • Summarized statistics (means, sd, interquartile ranges, ...) 	More than one option possible
Used data format(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .CSV • .RData • .txt • .json • etc. 	Data in structured and open-source format Structured by task, joint and direction → an example table can be found below. Save all values with 2 decimal points.
Nomenclature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent nomenclature, described in the marker model and list of performed tests 	Reference to the used nomenclature and/or marker model is sufficient
Encoded/Anonymized personal data		
Used data format(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .CSV • .RData • .txt • etc. 	Data in a structured and open-source format
Method of anonymization		As described in the metadata including responsible person / contact person who is listed in metadata.

Example table: Walking at self-selected speed, knee flexion/extension angles, normalized to the gait cycle

Subject ID	Right knee flex 0% of gait cycle [°]	Right knee flex 100% of gait cycle [°]
Sub01	5.26	17.95	80.63	5.84
Sub02	8.64	25.20	89.15	9.65
...

Set of calculated values:

The following table sets out the minimal specification for the calculated values for the different types of data which is needed when sharing data.

Type of data	Minimal specification of ... per participant (mean over number of trials)
Kinematics	In all 3 dimensions and for each joint: Range of motion [°] Maximal angle [°] Minimal angle [°]
Kinetics	In all 3 directions and for each joint: Minimal force [N] Maximal force [N] Minimal moment [Nmm] Maximal moment [Nmm]
EMG	For each muscle: Mean RMS value [%MVC or %RVC] Mean rectified amplitude value [mV]
Accelerometer	In all 3 directions and for each joint: Acceleration [m/s ²]
Inertial measurement unit	Body frame acceleration [m/s ²] Angular velocity [°/s]
Spatiotemporal parameters	Step length [m or % leg length] Step width [m or % pelvis width] Stride length [m or % leg length] Stride width [m or % pelvis width] Cadence [steps/min] Speed [m/s] Swing/stance phase [s or % gait cycle] Single/double support time [s or % gait cycle]
Plantar pressure	Peak pressure [N] Contact area [m]

6. References

- Creative commons*. (2019). [Online post]. <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/licenses/>
- Fossa Editorial Team. (2021, June 3). All About Permissive Licences. *Open Source License Compliance*. <https://fossa.com/blog/all-about-permissive-licenses/>
- International Organization for Standardization. (2024). *Date and time format*. <https://www.iso.org/iso-8601-date-and-time-format.html>
- Stall, S., Martone, M. E., Chandramouliswaran, I., Federer, L., Gautier, J., Gibson, J., Hahnel, M., Larkin, J., Pfeiffer, N., Sedora, B., Sim, I., Smith, T., Van Gulick, A. E., Walker, E., Wood, J., Zaringhalam, M., & Zigoni, A. (2023). *Generalist Repository Comparison Chart* (Version 3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7946938>